

International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research Transactions

(A Peer Reviewed Journal)

www.ijmrt.in

A Study on Employee Job Satisfaction (with special reference to aavin in madurai district)

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Abstract

Every human being possess him own unique resources, if properly channels it by supportive and supplement, ultimately for achieving organisation goals. As proper breathing and diet is necessary to healthy human being so as it contentment to the job satisfaction. This contentedness ultimately acts as a key factor to human resources development. The survey made regarding the job satisfaction in Aavin will facilitate and enables the management to know the perceptions and inner feelings regarding the job they are performing on day-to-day basis. The term job satisfaction reveals and focuses on the likes and dislikes of the employees of Aavin. This study tries to identify the causes for satisfaction and dissatisfaction among the employees in Aavin

Keywords: Employee feedback, Job satisfaction, Madurai, AAVIN.

1. Introduction

Research has been conducted in order to critically evaluate and examine the level of employees' satisfaction among the employees of Madurai aavin. The purpose of this study is also to observe and analyze the factors which create job satisfaction especially among the hardworking employees, and to find out the reasons of dissatisfaction if any. The results have shown that working environment, compensation, growth opportunities and training &

development are the most important significant factors which directly influences in affecting Job Satisfaction.

According to a number of literatures studied, lack of job satisfaction is a serious issue in various organizations and job dissatisfaction has become a major obstacle in employees' productivity and organization's growth. There are numbers of factors which can create job dissatisfaction among employees but in this study the very critical factors are discussed upon which the Madurai aavin management should really work on the job satisfaction of its employees. Productivity is closely related with performance of dairy cattle milk business units, but this performance is affected by factors such as organizational learning, market orientation and job satisfaction.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Gautama Kakaty and MoromiGogoi (2001) - "Employment and income opportunity in Dairy enterprises of Assam - A Case Study" have reported that animal husbandry plays a pivotal role in the agrarian economy of India. It is closely interlinked with the socio-economic matrix of rural society. The development of livestock sector has been receiving significant priority in India in the last two to three decades. It was found that dairy sector contributes significantly in generating employment opportunities and supplementing the income of small and marginal farmers providing by them food safety.

Mallikarjuna Reddy and Subramanyam (2002) - "Factors Affecting Productivity Gap in Dairy Farming" conducted a study on "Factors Affecting Productivity Gap in Dairy Farming". It has been observed that the farmers owned dairy animals has a higher entity of dry fodder but a lower level of green fodder concentrates as compared to the ration of farm-bred animals. The study concluded that the sound management practices and increased input use are the factors responsible for the yield gap in crossbred cows and murrah buffaloes. The contribution of management accounted for 20 per cent and contribution of feed accounted for 33 percent of the change in milk production of cross bred cows consequent upon a shift from farmer level practices to farm-level practices.

SCOPE OF THE STUDY

The study is conduct on the employees in the Madurai "Aavin". Job satisfaction is an important yield that employees work in organisation. The study made on the theme of job satisfaction will make known the factors of feelings of employees. It is an interesting and

important area for conducting research. This statement is useful to the management of the company to know the satisfaction level of employees and they can take method to increase productivity.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To identify the Socio-economic factors of employees in AAVIN.
- To identify the job satisfaction level of employees in AAVIN.
- To offer the finding and conclusions.

LIMITATION OF THE STUDY

Only 150 respondents are engaged to this research study. Time is one of the main constraints of the study. We met the employees whereas at work so they weren't able to spend much time to answering the question. The review includes all the limitation invents in the questionnaires from the research.

SAMPLE AREA

The research was conducted at Aavin in Madurai city.

DATA COLLECTION:

This is an experimental study based on the analysis method. The data were collected commencing both:

- Primary sources
- Secondary sources

PRIMARY DATA:

The primary data has been collected from aavin employees (in saathamangalam) by administrating a structured questionnaire by having face to face communication with employees.

SECONDARY DATA:

Apart from a primary data collection this will give theoretical basis, which can be obtainable from different sources such as textbooks, the records of aavin, journals, from library, from academic reports and internet is used for this learning.

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY:

The job satisfaction is psychological feeling of person. It is a personal feeling of an employee towards his job. It is difficult toward evaluate the satisfaction level of an employee.

Because it is intangible and complex bring together of cognitions and emotional and as well differs from one person toward another person. From the accessible tools, an effort is made to evaluate the satisfaction level amongst the employee of Aavin dairy to probable extend.

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

PROFILE OF THE RESPONENT

TABLE NO: 1.1
AGE OF THE RESPONDENT

SL.NO.	AGE OF THE RESPONDENT	NO. OF THE RESPONDENTS	PERCENT
1	Below 30	40	26.70%
2	31 – 40	54	36%
3	41 – 50	44	29.30%
4	Above 51	12	8%
TOTAL		150	100

Source: Primary data

INFERENCE:

In the table 1.1 it shows that, 26.7% of respondents were below 30 years, 36% of respondents were between 31-40 years, 29.3% of respondents were between 41-50 years and 8% of respondents were above 51 years. It was concluded that the (36%) respondents of 31-40 years age group were mostly involved in aavin dairy factory.

TABLE NO: 1.2
GENDER OF THE RESPONDENT

SL.NO.	GENDER	NO. OF THE RESPONDENTS	PERCENT
1	Male	97	64.70%
2	Female	53	35.30%
3	Transgender	0	0
TOTAL		150	100

Source: Primary data

INFERENCE:

In the table 1.2 it shows that, 64.7% of respondent are male, 35.3% of respondent are female, and 0% are transgender. It inferred majority (64.7%) of male respondent were mostly worked in aavin dairy factory.

TABLE NO: 1.3
MARTIAL STATUS OF THE RESPONDENT

SL.NO.	MARTIAL	NO. OF THE RESPONDENTS	PERCENT
1	Married	103	68.70%
2	Unmarried	47	31.30%
TOTAL		150	100

Source: Primary data

INFERENCE:

In the table 1.3 it can be seen, that 68.7% of respondent were married persons and 31.3% of respondent were unmarried persons. It was identified that (68.7%) most of the respondents are married persons.

TABLE NO: 1.4
EDUCATIONAL QUALIFICATION OF THE RSPONDENT

SL.NO.	PARTICULARS	NO. OF THE RESPONDENTS	PERCENT
1	Primary	3	2%
2	Secondary	17	11%
3	Higher secondary	34	23%
4	Under graduate	39	26%
5	Post graduate	27	18%
6	Diploma	18	12%
7	Uneducated	12	8%
TOTAL		150	100

Source: Primary data

INFERENCE:

In the table 1.4 it was found that, 2% of respondent were primary, 11% of respondent were secondary, 23% of respondent were higher secondary, 26% of respondent were under graduate, 18% of respondent were post graduate, 12% of respondent were diploma and 8% of respondent were uneducated. It was concluded that majority (26%) of respondent were under graduate.

TABLE NO: 1.5
FAMILY TYPE OF RESPONDENT

SL.NO.	PARTICULARS	NO. OF THE RESPONDENTS	PERCENT
1	Joint	72	48%
2	Nuclear	78	52%
TOTAL		150	100

Source: Primary data

INFERENCE:

In the table 1.5 it shows that, 48% of respondent were in joint family and 52% of respondent were in nuclear family. From the analysis concluded that many (52%) of the respondent were in nuclear family.

TABLE NO: 1.6
IMPORTANT JOB SATISFACTION FACTOR FOR RESPONDENT

SL.NO.	PARTICULARS	NO. OF THE RESPONDENTS	PERCENT
1	Salary	49	32.70%
2	Management	39	26%
3	Welfare benefits	35	23.30%
4	Working condition	27	18%
TOTAL		150	100

Source: Primary data

INFERENCE:

In the table 1.6 it was found that, 32.7% of respondent were preferred to salary, 26% of respondent were preferred to management, 23.3% of respondent were preferred to welfare benefits and 18% of respondent were preferred to working condition. It was concluded majority (32.7%) of the respondent choose salary factor was more important to have job satisfaction.

TABLE NO: 1.7
PURPOSE OF GOING JOB FOR THE RESPONDENT

SL.NO.	PARTICULARS	NO. OF THE RESPONDENTS	PERCENT
1	To run the family	47	31.30%
2	To increase standard of living	58	38.70%
3	To support family	45	30%
TOTAL		150	100

Source: Primary data

INFERENCE:

In the table it shows that, 31.3% of respondent were run the family, 38.7% of respondent were increase standard of living and 30% of respondent were support family. It was concluded majority (38.7%) of the respondent were purpose for going job to increase standard of living.

TABLE NO: 1.8
NATURE OF WORK FOR THE RESPONDENT

SL.NO.	PARTICULARS	NO. OF THE RESPONDENTS	PERCENT
1	Standing	62	41.30%
2	Sitting	26	17.30%
3	Writing	28	18.70%
4	With computer	34	22.70%
TOTAL		150	100

Source: Primary data

INFERENCE:

In the table was found that, 41.3% of respondent were standing work, 17.3% of respondent were sitting work, 18.7% of respondent were writing work and 22.7% of respondent were computer work. From the analysis concluded that many (41.3%) of the respondent nature of job were standing work.

TABLE NO: 1.9
LEAVE FACILITIES PROVIDE FOR RESPONDENT

SL.NO.	PARTICULARS	NO. OF THE RESPONDENTS	PERCENT
1	Casual leave only	37	24.70%
2	Casual leave and Medical leave	31	20.70%
3	Casual leave, Medical leave and Maternity leave	39	26%
4	Casual leave, Medical leave, Maternity leave and Religious leave	43	28.60%
TOTAL		150	100

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Source: Primary data

INFERENCE:

In the table it shows that, 24.7% of respondent were got casual leave, 20.7% of respondent were got casual & medical leave, 26% of respondent were got casual, medical & maternity leave and 28.6% of respondent were got casual, medical, maternity & religious leave. It inferred majority (28.6%) of the respondent were availed all leave facilities.

TABLE NO: 1.10
MODE OF PAYMENT FOR RESPONDENT

SL.NO.	PARTICULARS	NO. OF THE RESPONDENTS	PERCENT
1	Daily	15	10%
2	Weekly	14	9.30%
3	Monthly	121	80.70%
TOTAL		150	100

Source: Primary data

INFERENCE:

In the table it shows that, 10% of respondent were got a daily payment, 9.3% of respondent were got a weekly payment and 80.7% of respondent were got a monthly payment. It was concluded that majority (80.7%) of the respondent were received monthly payment.

TABLE NO: 1.11**LEVEL OF SATISFACTION REGARDING WORKING ENVIRONMENT**

SL. NO.	OPINION	NO. OF RESPONDENTS				PERCENT			
		ALW	F	ST	NVR	AL	F	ST	NVR
1	Co -operation of family member	78	51	10	11	52%	34%	6.7%	7.3%
2	Freedom to save the salary	44	72	21	13	29.3%	48%	14%	8.7%
3	Not feeling tired and bored with works	33	56	26	35	22%	37.3%	17.4%	23.3%
4	Getting satisfied increment	34	65	31	20	22.7%	43.3%	20.7%	13.3%

Source: Primary data

[ALW – Always; F – Frequently; ST – Sometimes; NVR – Never]

INFERENCE:

In the table it was found that, 52% of respondents were always got cooperation of family members else 7.3% of respondents were never got cooperation of family members and 48% of respondents have always freedom to save salary else 8.7% of respondents have never freedom to save the salary and 37.3% of respondent were always not feeling tired with works else 17.4% of respondents were never not feeling tired with works and 43.3% of respondent were always getting satisfied increment else 13.3% of respondent were never getting satisfied increment.

TABLE NO: 1.12**OVERALL JOB SATISFACTION**

SL.NO.	PARTICULARS	NO.OF RESPONDENTS		PERCENT	
		YES	NO	YES	NO
1	Have you satisfied with your salary & benefits	102	48	68%	32%
2	Are they providing you any reward regarding your performance	83	67	55.3%	44.7%
3	Overall you satisfied with your position in this company	114	36	76%	24%

Source: Primary data

INFERENCE:

In the table it was found that, 68% of respondent were have satisfied in salary else 32% of respondent were not satisfied in salary and 55.3% of respondent were got rewards else 44.7% of respondent were not got any rewards and 76% of respondent were overall satisfied for working in company else 24% were not overall satisfied for working in company. It was concluded that most of the respondent got salary benefits, rewards and said overall satisfied in this company.

LIKERT SCALING

TABLE NO: 1.13
RESPONDENT SATISFACTION REGARDING THE COMPANY

OPINION	EX	GD	NL	S	NS	MEAN SCORE	RANK
Opinion about company's objective	43	50	18	32	7	3.6	1
Opinion on your working condition	25	48	20	50	7	3.23	3
Satisfied with the policies, rules, regulation of the company	16	44	16	52	22	2.87	4
Feel the working environment	33	62	22	26	7	3.59	2

Source: Computed data

[Ex – Excellent; GD – Good; NL – Neutral; S – Satisfied; NS – Not Satisfied]

INFERENCE:

From the table 1.13 it shows that, opinion about company of respondents in each statement, in which it was found that the respondents are opinion about company objectives whereas the employees do not have any problems in opinion themselves so, it has high mean score of 3.6 and it was ranked as first. Satisfied with the policies, rules, regulation of the company, this opinion is average as most other opinion it has least mean score of 2.87 and it was ranked as last, because the respondents are not satisfy with the policies, rules, regulation of the company when compare to other opinion.

FINDINGS

- The age category of respondent were 36% in between 31-40, 8% of the respondent were in the age group above 51, it implies that most of the workers are between 31-40 age group.
- The gender of respondent were 97% of male workers, no respondent were in transgender, it was identified that most of the male employees are work in this factory.
- The marital status of respondent shows that 103 respondents were married, it was identified that 68.7% of the respondents were married persons.
- The education category of respondent, were percentage of under graduate respondent are 26% whereas the primary education respondent are 2%.
- From this analysis it shows that, 80.7% of respondent were brought monthly payment whereas 9.3% of respondent were brought weekly payment. Thus it was done that many of the respondent payment are to be monthly wise.
- From this study it was concluded that, opinion about company objectives has high mean score of 3.6 and it was ranked as first where employees have no any problems in company objectives while employees has not satisfied in company policies & rules.

SUGGESTIONS

- It has been found that, different income level has been follow by the workers, so the government has to standardize the income level as per employee salary in the basis of experience as well as working skills for all workers.
- Provision of reasonable salary plays a vital role in improving the standard of living. This single factor is important for an employee than any other. So, to must give satisfactory salary to the workers.
- Be aware of employee achievements with genuine appreciation. To offer rewards and recognition for employees as per efforts, skill & achievement.

CONCLUSION

The findings and suggestions are based on the review made and these points should be considered and steps should be taken in this observation to achieve higher growth. Skills in the workplace. Number of employees who have demonstrated great flexibility at times in coordinating with work and respondents are satisfied with accessible inter-employee communication. At AAVIN they follow a systematic

planning and analysis process to evaluate employee performance. From the analysis it was also noted that there is scope for developing aavin's business case. Finally, the respondent would like to conclude that aavin employees are satisfied with the work and organization.

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